

Attachment to the Study Report:

Questionnaire Script – Semi-Structured Interview Guide for Fishermen on Ovalau Island, Fiji, 2025

Introduction and Role

1. Can you briefly tell us about your role or work in Vatukalo?
2. How long have you lived here and who taught you how to fish?

Fishing grounds and practices

3. What are your top three fishing areas?
4. Where do you usually go fishing? What makes these areas important to you?
5. What is special about fishing in the reef passages?
6. What kinds of fish do you usually catch in the reef passages? Are there certain species that are common or important?
7. Are there times of the year when fishing in the reef passages is better?
8. What type of gear do you use for fishing in the reef passages? Has the gear changed overtime?

Knowledge of fish and environment

9. What are your top 5 best fish to catch?
10. What signs do you look for that tell you fish are present in a reef passage?
11. Have you noticed changes in the number or size of fish in the reef passages over the years?
12. Do some fish species seem more or less abundant now compared to the past?
13. Do you use the tides to fish? Incoming/outgoing tide? During which tide do you think more fish are moving in/between the reef passages? Why?

Local values of reef passages and fish

14. Are the reef passages important for the village?
15. What fishes are important to the community for income, culture, or food?
16. What fish usually sell faster?
17. Is it used for anything other than fishing? (related to culture, ceremonies?)
18. How do you see the role of younger fishers compared to older fishers in passages?

Perceptions of Research/ (B)RUVs

19. What kind of information about fish would be useful to you and your community?
20. How do you feel about using underwater videos to record fish in the reef passages?
21. Would underwater videos during different tides and depths be useful?
22. What do you think would be important for me to keep in mind when working in your fishing grounds?

Closing

23. What advice would you give me as someone studying fish in your waters?
24. Is there a story or experience you would like to share about fishing in your passages?
25. Is there anything else you would like to add, or remove from all that you have shared?